

L U M I AI Factory

LUMI AI Factory Service Center
Empowering Europe's AI Ecosystem

D6.3

AI Factory Hub Handbook

EuroHPC
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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
AI Campus	The AI Campus is part of the AI Factory Hub, serving a particular target group, students specialising in or interested in artificial intelligence. It consists of physical and virtual facilities that will first be established at the AI Factory Hub on Aalto University's campus in Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland. The AI campus and its activities and services provide a framework that attracts and nurtures talent, fosters interactive communities, and offers a range of activities to support and engage students.
AI Factory Hub	The AI Factory Hub is the main entity and the umbrella term for the events, training, and resources that the hub provides for its different target groups and stakeholders. It provides both physical and virtual co-working spaces that cater to the diverse needs and goals of various stakeholders, including startups, SMEs, scientific communities, talented students, HPC/AI support teams, incubators, and accelerators. The main site will be on the Aalto University campus in Espoo, Finland which is a central hub for AI research and coordination in Finland. The main site will be supported by subsidiary sites on other campuses and AI accelerator sites across the consortium partner states.
Digital Decade strategy	European Union's 2030 Policy Programme to achieve a human-centered, sustainable, and digitally transformed society by setting concrete targets for digital skills, digital infrastructures, the digitalization of businesses, and the digitalization of public services. Targets and further information here .
Ellis Institute Finland	Ellis Institute Finland is a newly established world-class research hub in AI and machine learning. It aims to develop an ecosystem of top talent, businesses, and investments in Finland, with fundamental machine learning research at its core. The Institute is part of the European Laboratory for Learning and Intelli-

	gent Systems (ELLIS), which aims to build a pan-European institution for machine learning research. The institute is under Aalto University and is located on the university campus in Otaniemi, Espoo. The Otaniemi AI Factory Hub will be established in the same floor with Ellis Institute. Official website of Ellis Institute Finland here .
HPC	High-Performance Computing - supercomputing resources for large-scale simulations and modelling
HPDA	High-Performance Data Analytics - infrastructure for processing massive datasets
LUMI AI Factory	The LUMI AI Factory is a pioneering service infrastructure and expert support center designed to accelerate AI innovation across Europe. It provides a seamless, open AI solution that combines world-class supercomputing, high-value data, and top-tier AI expertise — empowering startups, SMEs, researchers, and businesses to develop cutting-edge AI models, tools, and applications. Official website here .
LUMI AI Factory Service Center Project (LUMI AIF)	Project acronym LUMI AIF. The LUMI AI Factory Service Center project is part of the broader LUMI AI Factory initiative that integrates world-class computing, top talent and high-value datasets to accelerate AI innovation in Finland and across Europe. This ecosystem leverages the current LUMI supercomputer but is gearing up for the upcoming LUMI-AI system and the AI-optimised quantum experimental platform LUMI-IQ. More information here .
NAIC	The Norwegian AI Cloud. NAIC provides access to High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources and support for researchers, PhD students, educators, entrepreneurs, startups, and SMEs who are interested in exploring AI methodologies and developing advanced AI models and algorithms.
NRIS e-infrastructure	Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services is a collaboration between Sigma2 AS and the four universities NTNU, UiB, UiO og UiT, to offer resources and support providing high performance computing and data storage services to researchers affiliated with academic institutions in Norway.
QC	Quantum Computing - emerging quantum technologies for specialized computational problems
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises.

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Executive Summary

This handbook provides a strategic and practical guide for planning, establishing, and operating AI Factory Hubs within universities and research environments. It is intended to inspire institutions and stakeholders by presenting a concept of what an AI Factory Hub is, why it matters, and how it can be successfully implemented. The handbook offers adaptable frameworks, operational principles, and codes of conduct to support smooth and sustainable hub operations.

Drawing on the experiences of the LUMI AI Factory Service Center project (LUMI AIF), the handbook highlights best practices and lessons learned to guide new initiatives. The Otaniemi Hub in Espoo, Finland, which will be launched by the end of 2025, serves as the primary reference point for the network of the AI Factory Hubs. In addition, the Ostrava Hub in Ostrava, Czech Republic is currently in development and will be launched at a later stage, further expanding the AI Factory network. The plans for both hubs have been concretized and provide a strong foundation for future hubs. Institutions are encouraged to build upon these practices while tailoring them to their local features, networks, and ecosystems.

AI Factory Hubs are positioned within a wider ecosystem of national and European AI and HPC initiatives. Understanding this strategic landscape is essential for aligning with broader goals, engaging relevant stakeholders, and maximizing impact. Each hub is encouraged to identify key actors in its local ecosystem—such as universities, research centers, companies, and public agencies—and actively pursue collaboration.

By sharing practices, participating in joint initiatives, and supporting cross-border innovation, hubs contribute to the European AI Factory vision. Their integration into the LUMI AI Factory ecosystem and alignment with national and EU-level strategies position them as key drivers of digital transformation, research excellence, and capacity building in AI and high-performance computing.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this handbook is to provide a comprehensive guide for establishing and operating AI Factory Hubs within universities and research environments. The AI Factory Hub handbook is created to instruct staff on practicalities of the co-working spaces and student facilities to ensure smooth operation. It also includes codes of conduct for the premises. Drawing on the experiences of the LUMI AIF project, the handbook outlines practical frameworks, operational principles, and implementation strategies that support the creation and sustainable operation of such hubs. The creators of this handbook wish that it could inspire organisations in establishing new AI Factory Hubs.

The deliverable is structured in two parts. The first introduces the AI Factory Hub concept, while the second offers concrete examples through the handbooks of the Otaniemi and Ostrava hubs. Among these, the Otaniemi hub serves as the primary hub and reference point for the LUMI AI Factory network, providing the main foundation of practices and guidelines to be adopted and further developed in subsequent hubs. In addition, there are plans to establish new hubs at the University of Helsinki's Kumpula Campus and to launch hub activities in Kajaani, Finland in collaboration with CSC's local office and regional stakeholders. Hubs established after Otaniemi are encouraged to adopt and build upon the best practices identified there, ensuring consistency and scalability across the AI Factory Hub network, and bearing the local features, networks and ecosystems in mind.

This handbook brings together insights from both Finnish and Czech implementations, providing adaptable guidelines that acknowledge the diversity of institutional, cultural, and regional contexts in which hubs operate. Instead of prescribing rigid solutions, it emphasizes core principles and flexible practices that can be tailored to local needs while maintaining operational excellence.

Key topics include guidelines for establishing a hub, as well as the essential features derived from the AI Factory Hub concept that should be adapted to new environments. Institutions are encouraged to apply these recommendations within their specific context while upholding the shared values of accessibility, excellence, and collaboration.

1.1 Target Audiences and User Framework

This handbook addresses multiple stakeholder groups across different levels of engagement, that are categorised into three main groups: primary institutional stakeholders, the hub user community and secondary stakeholders. The categorisation follows the principles of a stakeholder segmentation framework, where different groups are identified according to their relationship to a project—in this case, an AI hub.

Each hub-establishing organisation determines which stakeholder groups are essential to their operations, based on their specific role and their connections within local and national networks.

Primary Institutional Stakeholders

- Directly involved in planning, managing or funding the hub:

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- Institutional leaders and project managers planning AI hub establishment.
- Hub coordinators and operational staff managing daily activities.
- University administrators and research infrastructure managers.
- Funding bodies and policy makers.

Hub User Community

- End-users of the hub's services:
 - Students: Undergraduate and graduate students, in addition to doctoral researchers requiring computational access and training.
 - Academic Staff: Faculty, researchers, and teaching staff seeking advanced computational support.
 - Industry Partners: Startups, SMEs, and large enterprises needing AI/HPC capabilities.
 - Public Sector: Government organizations and policy makers requiring evidence-based solutions.
 - General Public: Citizens and schools seeking AI education and awareness.

Secondary Stakeholders

- Partners and ecosystem actors who are indirectly involved:
 - Partner institutions within AI ecosystems.
 - Regional innovation centers and technology transfer offices.

1.2 Core Value Proposition

AI Factory Hubs deliver value through three integrated pillars:

1. Advanced Computational Infrastructure

- High-Performance Computing (HPC): Supercomputing resources for large-scale simulations and modelling.
- High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA): Infrastructure for processing and analysing massive datasets.
- Quantum Computing (QC): Emerging quantum technologies for specialized computational problems.
- Artificial Intelligence Systems: GPU clusters and specialized hardware for training and deploying AI models.

2. Human Expertise and Knowledge Transfer

- Access to specialists in HPC, AI, quantum computing, and data analytics.
- Mentorship for complex computational projects.
- Peer learning communities and research collaborations.
- Strategic consultation for computational research design.

3. Capacity Building and Knowledge Dissemination

- Advanced training programs for students, researchers and technical professionals.
- Specialized workshops on AI-related topics, for example HPC optimization, AI model development, and quantum algorithms.
- Educational outreach to inspire future researchers and inform stakeholders.
- Documentation and best practices for resource-efficient computing.

2. The AI Factory Hub Concept

This chapter introduces the concept of the AI Factory Hub, combining strategic vision with practical guidance for implementation. It provides a comprehensive overview of both the strategic and operational aspects involved in establishing and running a hub. The aim is to present the key components of the AI Factory Hub and support organisations in adapting their hub models to suit local needs and available resources.

2.1 Vision and Mission

An AI Factory Hub is a specialized organisational model for advancing high-performance computing (HPC) and AI capabilities within academic and research environments. It bridges cutting-edge computational infrastructure with diverse research communities, providing access to resources that would otherwise remain out of reach for individual researchers and institutions. Beyond its technical role, the hub is a place where people and ideas meet to create something new, fostering collaboration between researchers, students, and industry partners to share knowledge, experiment with emerging technologies, and co-develop innovative solutions. These interactions also enhance the visibility of the LUMI AI Factory and strengthen the European AI Factory ecosystem.

AI Factory Hubs envision a European research landscape where advanced computational capabilities serve as accessible catalysts for scientific discovery and innovation. The LUMI AIF project aims to provide a comprehensive and accessible service infrastructure that empowers AI start-ups, SMEs, researchers, and other public and private users to develop innovative European AI models and applications. By leveraging the established LUMI ecosystem and expanding it with AI-focused features, the hubs foster a thriving AI community that transcends borders and sectors, concentrating talent capable of competing globally.

The mission of AI Factory Hubs is to establish sustainable centers of excellence that:

- Expand availability of HPC, quantum computing, and AI infrastructure.
- Foster interdisciplinary collaboration between computational scientists, domain researchers, and industry partners.
- Accelerate the translation of computational research into practical applications.
- Build the next generation of computationally skilled researchers and professionals.

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By combining world-class computational capabilities with accessible entry points through learning opportunities and community engagement, AI Factory Hubs support innovation, knowledge exchange, and collaboration across Europe. They also provide guidance and specifications for establishing new hubs in consortium countries, promoting consistent practices, information sharing, and visibility within the European HPC network and stakeholder communities.

2.2 Strategic Objectives and Target Outcomes

Building on the vision and mission, this section outlines the strategic objectives, expected outcomes, and alignment of AI Factory Hubs with broader initiatives. It shows how hubs translate their vision into practical actions that support research, innovation, and collaboration.

AI Factory Hubs provide accessible HPC and AI resources while fostering research excellence, innovation, and sustainable ecosystem development. Their strategic objectives are:

Accessible Infrastructure

Hubs lower barriers to HPC and AI by offering simplified access procedures, tiered resource models matched to user expertise, and equitable allocation across disciplines and institutions.

Knowledge Transfer and Capacity Building

Hubs promote learning and skills development through workshops, modular training, best-practice repositories, and mentorship networks, building computational literacy across diverse disciplines.

Research Excellence and Innovation

Hubs support advanced research requiring large-scale computation, enable rapid experimentation with emerging technologies, facilitate novel AI applications, and encourage reproducible and open science practices.

Ecosystem Development

Hubs create communities of practice, foster partnerships with academia, industry, and the public sector, connect local innovation to European and global initiatives, and support spin-offs and research commercialization.

Sustainable Operations

Hubs develop diversified funding models, integrate with institutional strategies, and ensure long-term viability through continuous adaptation and demonstrated impact.

Target Outcomes

Hubs aim to generate measurable impact across four areas:

- **Scientific:** Increased research output, cross-disciplinary breakthroughs, and enhanced competitiveness.

- **Educational:** Expanded computational skills, integration of HPC and AI into curricula, and broader research literacy.
- **Economic:** Accelerated technology transfer, enhanced industry competitiveness, and creation of high-value jobs.
- **Societal:** AI solutions addressing critical challenges, improved public understanding of AI, and responsible, ethical AI development.

Alignment with Broader Initiatives

Hubs support European, national, and institutional priorities by:

- Contributing to European digital sovereignty, The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) objectives, and AI and Digital Decade strategies.
- Strengthening national research infrastructures and international competitiveness.
- Advancing university research strategies, interdisciplinary programs, and institutional visibility.

2.3 Success Metrics and Evaluation

The achievement of hub objectives can be measured using:

- **Quantitative metrics:** number of users, number of organised events, compute hours, publications, and trained individuals.
- **Qualitative assessments:** user satisfaction, research impact, and community engagement.
- **Long-term indicators:** sustainability, ecosystem growth, and societal benefits.

Regular monitoring of these metrics ensures hubs remain aligned with evolving research needs and continuously improve their impact. Additionally, feedback from users and visitors is an essential part of this process. Hubs should actively collect input through surveys, interviews, or informal discussions at key interaction points, such as after workshops, training sessions, or project collaborations. This feedback should guide the ongoing development of the hub and its services, helping to adapt offerings to user needs and priorities.

Each hub should define, according to its specific targets, reporting requirements, available tools, and resources, the extent to which user activity, satisfaction, and engagement are tracked and evaluated.

2.4 Code of Conduct

This code applies to all AI Factory Hub activities and spaces, both physical and virtual. Its goal is to create a safe, inclusive, and collaborative environment for learning, research, and innovation. Compliance with this code ensures that all hub activities—from training and workshops to co-working and online collaboration—support the hub’s mission and success.

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The code covers all hub facilities and events, online platforms and communities, interactions between community members and use of computational resources and AI tools.

2.4.1 Core Principles

- Respect, inclusion, and openness for all participants.
- Zero tolerance for harassment or discrimination.
- Transparency and fair recognition of contributions.
- Responsible and safe use of AI technologies.

2.4.2 Expected Behaviours

Community members are expected to maintain a constructive, respectful, and collaborative environment by:

- Communicating respectfully and giving space for others to contribute.
- Crediting authors, sources, datasets, and models appropriately.
- Criticizing ideas, not individuals.
- Following data protection rules and licensing agreements.
- Supporting newcomers and peers in their learning journey.
- Sharing knowledge while respecting confidentiality.
- Using resources efficiently and fairly.
- Reporting concerns or technical issues promptly (“See something → say something”).

2.4.3 Unacceptable Behaviours

Examples of behaviours that will not be tolerated:

- Harassment, sexist/racist/condescending language, threats.
- Unwanted contact, stalking, or deliberate disruption of events.
- Spreading harmful content (misinformation, malware).
- Misuse of system access or data (HPC resources, internal repositories).
- Violation of academic integrity or research ethics.

2.4.4 AI-Specific Guidelines

- Do not process personal or sensitive data without authorization and a legal basis.
- Label synthetic content and cite the model/tool used.
- Do not present model outputs as facts without verification; acknowledge limitations.
- Respect dataset/model licenses and intellectual property terms.
- Document methods and be transparent about AI use in research.

2.4.5 Privacy and Documentation

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- Respect designated “no recording” zones.
- Ask for consent before photographing individuals.
- Keep sensitive discussions (e.g., company data) within agreed circles.
- Follow institutional policies on data sharing and privacy.

2.5 General Layout and Facilities

The AI Factory Hub premises should support diverse activities while being functional, accessible, sustainable, and inviting. The hub is envisioned as a welcoming, cozy space—more like a lounge or living room than a traditional office—while still providing ergonomic working areas and dedicated spaces for collaboration and gatherings.

When establishing a local hub, the implementation team should carefully consider the available space, local needs, and resources. Benchmarking existing hubs within the AI Factory consortium and drawing inspiration from local ecosystem operations can help ensure that the space is both contextually relevant and aligned with the broader network’s goals.

Key Elements:

- Co-working areas: Flexible, comfortable spaces for collaborative work and interaction.
- Meeting & project rooms: Equipped for small teams, focused discussions, and planning.
- Quiet zones: Reserved for concentrated, individual work.
- Student zones: Spaces for study, learning, and self-directed exploration.
- Event spaces: Flexible areas for workshops, presentations, and community gatherings, supporting networking and exchange.

Depending on the hub’s size and primary purpose, it is important to ensure that there are enough suitable spaces to meet user needs effectively. Where possible, hubs should also explore opportunities to share facilities—such as large auditoriums, meeting rooms, or event spaces—with other units or organizations. Not all functions need to be addressed within the hub premises alone; leveraging existing infrastructure for special occasions or larger gatherings can enhance flexibility and reduce costs.

Environment & Design:

- Ergonomic workstations balanced with lounge-style areas for informal meetings.
- Collaborative surfaces (e.g., whiteboards, boards, screens).
- Reliable high-speed connectivity and access to shared resources.
- A visually appealing, slightly “eye-catching” design that feels welcoming yet professional for students, researchers, and industry visitors.
- Adaptable spaces that can shift between individual, group, and community activities.

Where possible, existing furniture, equipment, and materials within the host organization should be reused to reduce costs and environmental impact. Not everything needs to be newly acquired; thoughtful

reuse can contribute to both sustainability and a sense of continuity with the local context.

Accessibility & Sustainability:

Site Selection: When selecting premises, consider proximity to key user groups (students, researchers, industry partners), transport connections, accessibility for diverse user needs, and alignment with institutional sustainability and development strategies.

- Barrier-free access to all spaces, including entrances, restrooms, and event areas.
- Clear signage and navigation support for new visitors.
- Integration with public transport routes and bike access to reduce travel barriers.
- Energy-efficient lighting, heating, and cooling solutions.
- Flexible layouts that allow long-term use and reduce unnecessary refurbishments.

2.6 Roles and Responsibilities

A successful AI Factory Hub recognizes the diversity of its user base—from students and researchers to industry partners and visiting experts. Understanding the specific needs, expectations, and levels of experience of these groups is essential for providing the right kind of support, services, and engagement opportunities.

Clear roles and responsibilities help ensure smooth operations, a welcoming atmosphere, and a consistent user experience across all hub activities. Depending on the hub's phase (just launched or established) and the number of permanent staff, responsibilities and tasks can be allocated as needed. Each hub should define roles and responsibilities in a way that best suits its operational context, including how the Hub Manager and staff share responsibilities.

Hub Manager Responsibilities

- Maintains a strategic overview of the hub's operations, ensuring activities are aligned with its purpose and that the hub effectively serves its users.
- Engages with stakeholders and identifies new, relevant target groups to expand the hub's reach and impact.
- Represents and promotes the hub's operations and best practices for relevant stakeholders.
- Is familiar with the hub's routines, opening hours, training schedules, and services, and communicates these to the co-workers to ensure smooth operations.
- Maintains order and ensures compliance with hub rules.
- Identifies resource needs and reports operational issues occurring in the hub.
- Coordinates the feedback collection process and ensures the feedback is processed and implemented in future activities.

Support Staff / Co-Workers

- Visible and present at the on-site hub, and the presence should also be coordinated with the virtual hub to ensure continuous support.
- Welcome and guide users to the appropriate experts or services.
- Provide technical or administrative support.
- Assist with onboarding new users, including guidance on hub activities, premises, guidelines and available support.
- Support events, workshops, and training sessions.
- Register hub users and collecting feedback from them.
- Report operational issues occurring in the hub.

2.7 Engagement and Programs

AI Factory Hubs aim to create inspiring spaces for learning, collaboration, and innovation. To engage hub users and stakeholders:

Events and Activities

- Examples of events and activities: workshops, seminars, hackathons, and networking events.
- Target groups: students, researchers, industry, and public stakeholders.
- When planning events, consider audience, timing, capacity, and accessibility.
- Think about what kind of value the events bring to the target groups and how they serve the hub's role, vision, and mission in the ecosystem.
- Ask the target groups about their needs and wishes regarding the events.
- By offering hybrid and remote events, there is a possibility to reach wider audiences and to serve target groups independent of time and place.

Scheduling Principles

- Annual or quarterly planning to ensure balanced programming.
- Keep the target groups in mind when drafting the annual plan.
- Flexibility to respond to emerging research opportunities or user needs.
- Consider target audience, technical background and accessibility needs.
- Utilize appropriate spaces based on event scale and purpose.
- Ensure inclusive participation with language support when needed.
- Connect with regional innovation ecosystem.
- Collect participant feedback for continuous improvement.

Promotion and Feedback

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- Ensure program visibility and findability—whether through a shared calendar, website, mailing list, or bulletin board—developed in collaboration with experts involved in training and skills development.
- Collect feedback from participants on satisfaction, participation, and improvement ideas.
- Use feedback to develop new activities, adapt schedules, and enhance services.

Training and Learning Opportunities

- Target audiences: students, researchers, and professionals.
- Subject areas: HPC, AI methods, domain-specific applications.
- Delivery modes: on-site, virtual, or hybrid formats depending on resources and user needs.
- Training programs and experimentation should be supported by a secured and controlled environment, that enables safe testing and development of AI tools, models and workflows.

2.8 Membership, Virtual Collaboration and Community Processes

The AI Factory Hub community includes both on-site and virtual participants. To ensure smooth collaboration and a safe, supportive environment, the following processes apply across all activities and platforms. These guidelines and actions can be adapted based on the specific needs, tools, and context of each hub. Flexibility is encouraged to ensure alignment with local practices and available resources.

Virtual Co-Working

- Remote access to shared computational resources may be provided when appropriate.
- Collaboration tools (video conferencing, project management platforms, booking systems) support hybrid and online activities.
- The same Code of Conduct applies to all virtual environments as in physical spaces.

Access to HPC Resources

- When planning hub features, communication and guidance regarding access to HPC resources should be taken into consideration.
- The hub's target groups and users should be considered. It is also essential to choose communication channels that effectively reach potential hub users.
- Communicate clearly with hub users and ensure that the coordinator and/or hub staff can guide visitors on the general requirements that must be met to gain access to the resources.
- Walk-in basis during opening hours in the on-site hubs. Opening hours to be defined by the hosting organisation.

Registration and Hub Access

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Please take the following into account when planning and implementing hub practices, whether for the on-site premises or the virtual hub environment:

- Registration required for both virtual and on-site hub visitors and users.
- All new members should review and agree to the Code of Conduct at the time of the registration.
- Information collected from hub visitors and users for project reporting and service improvement includes name, affiliation, purpose of visit.
- All activities will be conducted in accordance with EU law to ensure data protection.
- Orientation: Introduction to hub resources, expectations, reporting mechanisms, and support channels. This can be conducted by the hub manager or another co-worker. A virtual version is also possible, e.g. an introduction video.
- Community Access: Members are added to relevant collaboration platforms and mailing lists.
- Continuous Reinforcement: Regular reminders at events, updates on policies, and refresher training when needed.

Reporting and Support

- On-site: Issues can be raised directly with the Hub Coordinator.
- Online: Reports can be made via the designated email address or community channel. Urgent cases: Call building security or the emergency contact provided.
- Anonymous: Reports may also be submitted through institutional systems.
- Response: All reports are handled confidentially, fairly, and promptly, with support offered to affected individuals.

Enforcement

- Progressive Response:
 - Verbal or written warning.
 - Temporary suspension of access.
 - Exclusion from specific activities.
 - Permanent ban from hub services.
 - Organizers may act immediately in serious cases to ensure community safety.
- Appeals can be submitted to designated governance or leadership contacts.

Offboarding

- **Voluntary Departure:**
 - Return any borrowed equipment or access cards.
 - Document ongoing projects and hand over responsibilities.
 - Provide feedback through an exit interview (optional).
 - Option to remain connected to the community network as an alumni (optional).
- **Involuntary Removal:**
 - Immediate revocation of access in cases of serious violation.
 - Clear communication of reasons and documentation of the incident.

- Possibility of reinstatement after review on a case-by-case basis.

2.9 Governance and Feedback

Effective governance and continuous feedback are essential for maintaining a well-functioning AI Factory Hub. While governance also includes aspects such as funding, strategic planning, and overall management, this section focuses on the practical operational procedures that support day-to-day decision-making and user engagement.

This section complements Section 2.3 (Success Metrics and Evaluation) by outlining how hubs can implement transparent structures and feedback loops to ensure responsiveness, accountability, and continuous improvement.

Hubs should establish a clear and transparent governance structure, along with regular feedback mechanisms, including:

- Decision-making procedures for operations, events, and resource allocation.
- Continuous feedback collection from users and visitors through surveys, informal discussions, or digital channels.
- Feedback-driven improvements to hub layout, services, and activities.
- Monitoring of success metrics, such as user numbers, satisfaction levels, and research outputs.

2.10 Ecosystem Context and Strategic Positioning

AI Factory Hubs operate within a broader ecosystem of national and European AI and HPC initiatives. Understanding this context is essential for strategic alignment, stakeholder engagement, and maximizing impact. Each hub should identify key organizations and actors in its local ecosystem—such as universities, research centers, companies, and public agencies—and actively seek collaboration opportunities. These partnerships not only strengthen the hub’s local relevance but also contribute to the broader European AI Factory vision.

By sharing practices, participating in joint initiatives, and supporting cross-border innovation, hubs play a vital role in shaping a connected and forward-looking AI ecosystem. Recognizing the hub’s position within this landscape helps guide decision-making, align with strategic objectives, and ensure meaningful contributions at both national and European levels.

Key considerations include:

- The hub’s role within the LUMI AI Factory ecosystem.
- Its connection to European and national AI/HPC initiatives.
- Key stakeholders and organizations to engage with (e.g., universities, research institutes, companies, public sector).

- The importance of understanding the hub’s position in the broader landscape to maximize impact and collaboration.
- Reference to other chapters (e.g., governance, engagement, strategic objectives).

2.11 Integration with National AI Ecosystems and Service Centres – Example: Norway

The purpose of this section is to provide an example of a potential future integration with a national AI ecosystem. It has been recognised in the LUMI AIF that the success of the AI Factory Hubs also depends on their ability to align with and extend national AI ecosystems. National service centers act as the entry points for researchers, public administration, and industry, and ensure that investments at the European level are anchored in domestic priorities.

Norway provides a concrete example through the Norwegian AI Factory, which is an ecosystem and service center, coordinated by Sigma2 and closely linked with the Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC) and NRIS e-infrastructure. This national ecosystem is embedded within the LUMI AIF, and its role is to ensure seamless interoperability between Norwegian users and the wider AI Factory Hub network.

The integration operates on two reciprocal axes. Firstly, it makes Norwegian NAIC services accessible via the hub. This includes AI-ready virtual machine images, model caching and sharing platforms, and an AI-HPC training environment for researchers, IT professionals and students. Additionally, it provides benchmarking services, tools for assessing AI workloads, and trusted data environments for handling sensitive datasets.

Secondly, the integration enables Norwegian users to access hub-level services. Researchers, SMEs, and public sector actors in Norway gain streamlined access to LUMI AIF resources, such as large-scale model training, federated learning frameworks, and pan-European datasets. This is facilitated via harmonised user portals, aligned allocation processes, and interoperable APIs, ensuring that users can move seamlessly between national and hub-level services.

To sustain this bidirectional integration, LUMI AIF and the Norwegian service center coordinate in three areas:

- **Technical interoperability:** common standards for authentication, data access, and containerised workflows to ensure portability and compliance.
- **Training and skills:** co-branded workshops, hackathons, and curricula that bridge national training with LUMI AIF’s pan-European programme.
- **Governance:** regular exchange between LUMI AIF hub leadership and national service center representatives to align priorities, avoid duplication, and ensure reciprocal benefit.

This model shows how a national ecosystem, anchored in existing infrastructures and competences, can both enrich and benefit from the AI Factory Hub network. It provides a blueprint for other consortium members to structure their national–European integration.

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3. AI Factory Hub Otaniemi Guide

This chapter introduces the AI Factory Hub Otaniemi, a collaborative space designed to support students, researchers, and professionals working in the field of artificial intelligence. It provides practical guidance for hub visitors and users on:

- What the hub offers.
- Who can use the facilities.
- How to operate within the space.

3.1 Hub Overview

Located on the 4th floor of Maarintie 8 in Espoo—on the same floor as the Ellis Institute Finland, a world-class AI research center—the AI Factory Hub Otaniemi offers a versatile and engaging environment. It includes individual work desks, meeting rooms, and open spaces for training, events and informal gatherings, fostering a vibrant and collaborative atmosphere.

The hub is intended for students, researchers, experts, company representatives, and other stakeholders connected to the LUMI AI Factory network. It supports both individual work and community-building through its services and support, workshops, events, and training sessions. A virtual hub will also be established, enabling remote participation regardless of the physical location.

The AI Campus, as part of the AI Factory Hub, focuses on engaging students who are interested in AI and HPC. Through its activities and services, the campus builds a framework that attracts and nurtures talent, fosters interactive communities, and offers a range of opportunities to support and engage students.

Location: AI Factory Hub Otaniemi, 4th floor, Maarintie 8, Espoo, Finland

Environment

- ~121 m² dedicated to the AI Factory Hub including individual work desks and open space for trainings and events.
- Meeting rooms can be booked from the Ellis Institute premises on the same floor.
- Additional premises on the 4th floor: Sauna and terrace available upon request for special occasions.
- Priority system based on user classification and project needs.
- Online booking system for all spaces and equipment.

Target Users

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Otaniemi AI Factory Hub welcomes individuals, such as students and experts, as well as members of companies and organisations in the LUMI AI Factory ecosystem.

- Students - Whether beginning a bachelor's, pursuing a PhD, or anywhere in between, the hubs offer access to tools, training, and a community to grow the skills.
- Researchers and academic staff – Opportunities to strengthen projects with advanced computing power and expert support.
- Startups and companies - from small teams to SMEs and large enterprises, the hub provides possibilities to test and scale AI ideas with world-class resources.
- Government organisations and public sector – Opportunities to come up with solutions that benefit society.

Special Features

- Access to HPC, QC and LUMI AI Factory resources under certain conditions and terms. These will be clarified and communicated to hub users as soon as the registration systems and resource allocations have been defined. This is expected to happen by the end of 2025.
- Expert support and guidance. Examples include the possibility to book a time slot for consulting a LUMI AIF expert and the access to the self-learning materials. Further instruction to be updated by the end of 2025.
- AI Campus programs for students interested in artificial intelligence, including training and workshops.
- Interaction and matchmaking with industry.

Figure 1 Maarintie 8 from outside

3.2 Contacting the AI Factory Hub

General Contact

- General Inquiries: Until the launch, eeva.harjula@csc.fi or lumi-aif-wp6@postit.csc.fi
- Hub Coordinator: [Contact to be updated upon recruitment]
- Project Leadership: Eeva Harjula (CSC), project manager for AI Hubs; Juhani Huttunen (CSC), Lead of LUMI AI Factory Ecosystem Development
- AI Campus Activities: [email to be established]

Campus Maps, Public Transport, Parking and Opening Hours: Further information about the [Maarintie 8 building](#) and [getting around in Otaniemi Campus](#).

Figure 2 Maarintie 8 on the map

Physical Accessibility

- Building reception on the 1st floor in the main lobby of the Maarintie 8 building.
- Visitor registration required at reception.
- Building equipped for accessibility needs. Please contact custodians at tuasvahtimestarit@aalto.fi or +358504723222.

3.3 Visiting the Otaniemi AI Factory Hub

The details regarding visits will be defined and communicated to hub visitors by the launch. In the visiting guidelines, the principles from section 2.8 — Membership, Virtual Collaboration and Community Processes — will be considered, applied to the Otaniemi Hub practices, and communicated to its visitors and users.

3.3.1 Overview for Otaniemi Hub visitors

- General opening hours from Monday to Friday, 8:00 AM – 17:00 PM.
- Extended access available for registered users and special programs. Flexible scheduling for events and workshops.
- Dedicated time slots for specific target groups, such as expert support services, may be introduced in the future. Details will be announced once the scheduling and formats are confirmed.
- Simple registration for project reporting and service improvement is required from all hub visitors and users.
 - Information collected: name, affiliation, purpose of visit.

3.4 Available Services and Support for Hub Visitors and Users

3.4.1 Expert Support

The Otaniemi Hub aims to spread knowledge and foster innovation within both the hub network and the broader LUMI AI Factory ecosystem. Registered users engaged in AI-related skill development, studies or RDI (research, development and innovation) can access selected resources and services provided by the LUMI AI Factory. These include, for example, computing capacity, data services and AI computing tools. The following sections categorize the planned services and support and describe how the hub wants to engage with its visitors.

AI Computing Capacity

- Different level of computing packages are offered for various needs: packages suitable for training conventional machine learning models, finetuning large language models, or combining quantum computing and AI or HPC computing.

Access to Data

- Suitable solutions for different demands: Datasets-as-a-Service, storage for large datasets, storage for sensitive dataset, support for locating and acquiring new data to mention some examples.

AI Computing Services

- AI model service and packages for cloud infrastructure or data storage.

Support for AI Adoption in Companies

- For industry representatives the hub offers analysis and report to identify the needs and recommended services.
- Support for starting large scale AI computing or for applying computing or data resources

- Support for HPC and AI project implementation.
- Try & Buy for small computing project is provided free of charge.

3.4.2 Training Activities and skills development

- Training is tailored to target groups' needs for added value and knowledge sharing.
- Workshops, courses, and hackathons are organized to promote learning and collaboration in AI.
- Events boost engagement and highlight the hub's expertise in cutting-edge AI.
- Example topics include fundamentals of AI, large-scale AI, and high-performance computing (HPC).
- Participants gain access to online training materials and the virtual hub environment.

Study Groups and Peer Tutoring

- For bachelor, master, and PhD students

Collaborative Projects

- Seminars and joint initiatives with LUMI AI Factory ecosystem including various stakeholders from relevant AI related organizations, including higher education institutions, start-ups and SMEs, industry representatives etc.

3.5 Events and Engagement

To support and engage hub users—including students, industry and other stakeholders—a wide range of activities will be offered at the Otaniemi AI Factory Hub.

Details and registration to the events will be available in the training calendar, which will be synchronised with Work Package 1, responsible for training and skills development. The calendar will be published on the LUMI AIF website, scheduled to launch by the end of September 2025.

The Otaniemi Hub welcomes companies, student organizations, and research groups to host events in the premises. Whether it's a workshop, seminar, hackathon, meet-and-greet, or a completely new concept, the hub staff is enthusiastic about exploring ideas and developing them collaboratively. Organisers will receive support from the hub to bring their ideas to life, utilising the hubs' facilities, expertise, and community to ensure success. The principles guiding engagement and programs can be seen in section 2.7 — Engagement and Programs — of this document.

Please find below examples of the types of events the Otaniemi AI Factory Hub is eager to promote and host.

Networking Events

- Student-industry connection events for internships and career opportunities.
- Research partnership meetings for academic-business collaboration.
- Regional innovation meetings for ecosystem development.

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- International connections through LUMI consortium events.

Matchmaking

Events

Various networking events provide exposure to current research, industry trends, and expert insights. The strong networks surrounding CSC, Ellis, Aalto University, University of Helsinki and AI Finland create a uniquely attractive entity in Finland, making it easier to bring in visitors and renowned speakers. Leveraging these connections will strengthen engagement opportunities and position the AI Hub as a key destination for collaboration and knowledge exchange.

- Connect companies with students and researchers.
- Facilitate joint projects and technology transfer.
- Support startup development and mentorship programs.
- Strengthen the LUMI AI Factory ecosystem.

Trainings, Workshops, and Study Groups

- Modular AI-related sessions, updated regularly.
- Include hands-on exercises and practical use of supercomputers.

Workshops, courses, and hackathons on AI-related topics, from basics of deep learning to developing innovative AI solutions using the LUMI and LUMI-AI supercomputers. A complete and regularly updated schedule will be maintained and published on the LUMI AI Factory's website.

To enhance learning and encourage mutual support among bachelor's, master's, and PhD students from fields like computer, communication, and information sciences, specializing in areas such as machine learning, data science, and AI.

Other Collaborative Activities

- Seminars, joint events, summer schools and projects with partner institutes and networks.
- Strengthen the AI Factory Ecosystem and engagement opportunities.

3.6 Code of Conduct

- Refer to Section 2.4 in the main AI Factory Hub Concept for full guidelines.
- This section serves as a reminder of ethical and professional conduct, ensuring a safe, inclusive, and respectful environment for all users.

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4. AI Hub Ostrava Guide

IT₄Innovations National Supercomputing Center (IT₄I) will establish a dedicated AI Factory Hub at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (VSB-TUO). AI Factory Hub activities will be closely linked to those of the AI Campus.

4.1 Hub Overview

Main location: AI Factory Hub Ostrava, IT₄Innovations National Supercomputing Center at VŠB-TUO, Studentská 6231/1B, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

Environment: The hub encompasses multiple spaces across the IT₄Innovations building:

- 4th floor (~30 m²): Dedicated hub space for consultations and collaborative work.
- Room 237 (2nd floor): Training room for workshops and courses.
- Atrium (3rd floor): Event space with 50+ person capacity.
- Additional facilities available through VŠB-TU Ostrava departments.

Target Users: Students, researchers, academic staff, companies, esp. start-ups and SMEs, and other stakeholders especially active within the region. The hub will also engage with the general public through educational outreach programs.

Special Features:

- Access to HPC, QC and LUMI AI Factory resources.
- AI Campus programs for students specializing in artificial intelligence.
- Strong integration with local industry and educational institutions.

4.2 Contacting the AI Factory Hub

General Contact:

- Hub Coordinator: [Contact to be updated upon recruitment]
- Project Leadership: Martin Duda (Project Leader)
- AI Campus Activities: Karin Pešatová
- General Inquiries: [email to be established]

Physical Accessibility:

- Building reception at IT₄Innovations, Studentská 6231/1B, Ostrava-Poruba.
- Visitor registration required at reception.
- On-site parking available.
- Building equipped for accessibility needs.

Campus Maps and Access: [VSB-TUO campus map](#)

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4.3 Visiting the Hub

All details and procedures described in Chapter 2.8 (“Membership, Virtual Collaboration and Community Processes”) apply. Here only Ostrava-specific procedures are listed:

4.3.1 Overview for Ostrava Hub visitors

- Standard hours: Monday to Friday, 8:00 AM - 6:00 PM.
- Available spaces: individual work desks, meeting areas, training room, event space.
- Online booking system for all spaces and equipment.
- Extended access available for registered users and special programs.
- Flexible scheduling for events and workshops.
- Holiday schedule aligned with VŠB-TU Ostrava academic calendar.

4.4 Users, Guidelines, and Roles

For roles, responsibilities, and expectations, refer to Chapter 2.6 (“Roles and Responsibilities”). Ostrava-specifics are outlined below:

4.4.1 User Groups

- Staff and co-workers: LUMI AI Factory project team, IT4Innovations specialists.
- Hub Coordinator and support staff.
- Students from VŠB-TU Ostrava and partner institutions.
- Industry partners and regional stakeholders.
- Visitors and general public for specific programs.

4.4.2 AI Hub Coordinator

- Welcomes visitors and supports regular users.
- Facilitates access to resources and expertise.
- Connects users with IT4Innovations specialists.
- Ensures productive and inclusive environment.
- Collects feedback for continuous service improvement.

4.5 Available Services and Support

Expert Support:

- Research consultation for AI integration and HPC optimization.
- Technical mentorship for challenging projects.
- Facilitating industry advisory for business applications.
- Academic support for curriculum development and thesis supervision.
- Grant application assistance.

Training Activities:

- Educational events on the practical use of AI.

- Lectures promoting technological insights.
- Advanced courses to use supercomputers for AI projects.
- Hands-on hackathons for companies as well as for students.

Study Groups and Collaboration:

- Student-led learning communities across academic levels.
- Research presentation opportunities.
- Academic seminars and industry networking events.

Note: A sandbox model will be considered to tested for selected target groups, enabling initial testing of access to supercomputing capacities and other support tools.

4.6 Events and Engagement

Please refer to Chapter 2.7 (“Engagement and Programs”) for general planning principles, types of events, and engagement strategies. Ostrava-specific event types include:

- Research partnership meetings for academic-business collaboration.
- Regional innovation meetings for ecosystem development.
- International connections through LUMI AI Factories consortium events.
- Public engagement and high school outreach activities.

4.7 Regional Integration

The Ostrava hub serves as a key node in the Moravian-Silesian Region's innovation ecosystem:

Educational Partnerships:

- Deep integration with other VŠB-TU Ostrava departments.
- Collaboration with regional universities and high schools.

Connections with Industry and other Stakeholders:

- Integration with local business networks such as chambers of commerce.
- Cooperation on joint activities with other relevant entities supporting AI (such as Cerna.AI, Czech Association for Artificial Intelligence).
- Support for innovation centers, incubators, and accelerators.

4.8 Code of Conduct

- Refer to Chapter 2.4 in the main AI Factory Hub Concept for full guidelines.
- This section serves as a reminder of ethical and professional conduct, ensuring a safe, inclusive, and respectful environment for all users.

